

Synthesis of geranyl *N*-dimethylallylanthranilate, a new antimicrobial natural product from *Esenbeckia yaaxhokob*

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Abstract : A convenient synthesis of geranyl *N*-dimethylallylanthranilate **1**, utilizing DMAP mediated esterification of isatoic anhydride **2** with geraniol **3** and subsequent *N*-alkylation of the resulting ester **4** using tetrabutylammonium iodide with 3,3-dimethylallyl bromide **5** has been achieved in 88.2% yield. The identity with the naturally occurring compound was established on the basis of ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR data.

Keywords : Esterification, *N*-alkylation, geraniol.

Esenbeckia yaaxhokob is a plant growing in Yucatan, Mexico and has been employed for treating gastrointestinal ailments¹. Bernice Aguilar-Guadarrama *et al.* through a bioactivity guided fractionation from the acetone extract of the leaves of *Esenbeckia yaaxhokob*, isolated the first *N*- and *O*-prenylated anthranilate, geranyl *N*-dimethylallylanthranilate **1**². They also carried out the antimicrobial activity of the new compound **1** and found it to exhibit moderate activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*. On the basis of the analytical and spectral analysis, structure **1** was assigned to the new compound. As a final and conformational proof for this natural product, we undertook its synthesis and were successful in achieving our goal as depicted in Scheme 1. The synthesis is not only of academic interest but also a route for bulk production of the prenylated anthranilate **1**, which is obtainable from the natural source in trace amount².

Results and discussion

As shown in Scheme 1, geranyl *N*-dimethylallylanthranilate **1** has been synthesized from isatoic anhydride **2**, a good precursor for the synthesis of anthranilate esters, in two steps. Reaction of isatoic anhydride **2** with geraniol **3** in the presence of 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP), as catalyst gave rise to geranyl anthranilate ester **4** in 70% yield³. *N*-Alkylation of the resulting ester **4** with 3,3-dimethylallyl bromide **5** using tetrabutylammonium iodide as the phase transfer catalyst furnished the target compound **1** in 88.2% yield⁴. The spectral data of the synthesized compound **1** agree well with that reported in the literature².

Scheme 1. Synthesis of geranyl *N*-dimethylallylanthranilate.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR (DEPT) were recorded in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz on Varian FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to TMS. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were determined on VG 70S with an 11-250 J+ data system. All organic solvents were dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. Silica gel impregnated with calcium sulfate was used for TLC.

(*E*)-3,7-Dimethyl octa-2,6-dienyl 2-aminobenzoate (**4**) : To a mixture of isatoic anhydride **2** (1.63 g, 10 mmol) and 4-dimethylaminopyridine (0.122 g, 1 mmol), under the blanket of dry N₂, was added dry dimethylformamide (10 mL) via a syringe. After 1 min, geraniol **3** (1.87 mL, 11 mmol) was added with immediate evolution of carbon dioxide. The reaction mixture was heated to 60 °C for 3 h cooled and then partitioned between ethylacetate (50 mL) and water (50 mL). The aqueous layer was extracted with additional ethyl acetate and organic layer was sepa-

Note

rated. The combined organic extracts were washed with brine (2×50 mL), dried with sodium sulfate, filtered and evaporated to give **4** as yellow solid; yield 2 g, (70%; m.p. 140–141 °C; ν_{\max} 3340, 3255, 2969, 2921, 2859, 1710, 1601, 1453, 770, 705 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR δ (ppm) 8.28 (1H, dd, J 8.0, 1.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.40–7.36 (3H, m, Ar-H), 5.20 (1H, bt, J 7.2 Hz), 4.95 (1H, bs), 3.72 (2H, bs), 1.95 (4H, s), 1.65 (3H, s), 1.55 (6H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 17.2, 19.6, 25.6, 26.4, 39.5, 60.4, 110.2, 116.2, 118.7, 123.0, 123.5, 130.7, 132.1, 133.9, 135.8, 150.8, 166.0.

(*E*)-(3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dienyl-2-(3-methylbut-2-enylamino)benzoate (**1**): Bu_4NI (0.08 g, 0.3 mmol), triethylamine (0.45 mL, 3 mmol), ester **4** (0.5 g, 1.7 mmol) and 3,3-dimethyl allyl bromide **5** (0.24 g, 1.64 mmol) were dissolved in sufficient dry tetrahydrofuran. The mixture was stirred at 20 °C for 3 h when TLC indicated the absence of starting halide. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ether and washed with water. The combined organic extracts were dried and the solvent evaporated to furnish **1** as the oil with spectral data comparable to the literature details²; yield 0.537 g, (88.2%); λ_{\max} (ϵ) 242 (2098), 281 (694), 348 (328) nm; ν_{\max} 3425, 2969, 2924, 2859, 1710, 1601, 1453, 770, 705 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR δ (ppm) 8.28 (1H, dd, J 8.0, 1.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.55–7.36 (3H, m, Ar-H), 5.20 (1H, bt, J 7.2 Hz), 5.18 (1H, bt, J 7.2 Hz), 4.95 (1H, bs), 4.1 (1H, bs, -NH : exchangeable with D_2O), 3.72 (2H, bs), 3.60 (2H, bs), 1.95 (4H, s), 1.65 (6H, bs), 1.50 (9H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , multiplicities by the DEPT pulse sequences) δ 168.10 (s, C-

2a), 148.38 (s, C-1), 143.26 (s, C-3'), 139.41 (s, C-3''), 133.19 (d, C-5), 131.08 (s, C-7'), 131.61 (d, C-3), 127.21 (d, C-4), 127.26 (s, C-2), 123.32 (d, C-6'), 123.01 (d, C-6), 116.09 (d, C-2'), 116.63 (d, C-2''), 53.19 (t, C-1'), 53.09 (t, C-1''), 39.56 (t, C-4'), 26.23 (t, C-5'), 25.95 (q, C-4''), 25.79 (q, C-8'), 18.02 (q, C-5''), 17.53 (q, C-10'), 16.26 (q, C-9'); EI-MS (70 eV) [M^+] 341, 272, 204, 186, 137, 119, 69 (Found : C, 77.49; H, 9.20; N, 4.18. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{31}\text{NO}_2$ requires : C, 77.38; H, 9.15; N, 4.10%).

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